

Molecular Docking of Selective Dopamine D_{1A} Receptor Agonists: Achieving Binding Energies Exceeding –11 kcal/mol

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18848529>

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Abstract

Dopamine receptor D_{1A} agonist –11.1 kcal/mol is a flagship for docking selective and high-affinity scaffolds. The structure features an enlarged aromatic core, a compressed pro-ethylamine group in the form of imidazoline, and a cyclopentane complementary imidazole scaffold. This structure, with its special radical configuration, allows for stacking in the aromatic ring of dopamine, positioning the amino group opposite D-103, enabling fork-like docking of hydrogen and lipophilic bonds. Also, in the aromatic ring, bonds are formed with hydroxyls, ketones, or aldehydes, with syrins responsible for binding the phenolic hydroxyls of dopamine or their lipophilic adjacent amino acid residues in the presence of lipophilic radicals (figure1).

Dopamine receptor D_{1A} agonist –11.1 kcal/mol shows a decrease in affinity on the type 2 receptor to 9.1 kcal/mol, the structure is located in the receptor with its back side up and is in a state close to false triggering (figure2).

Thus, high selectivity, as well as high affinity of the structure, are a consequence of more complete agonistic filling of the receptor pocket.

Unlike the asymmetrical imidazoline core, one of the additional cores is completely symmetrical and also represents a highly available diimidazole. The symmetry of this structure, with an affinity of -10 kcal/mol (figure3), reduced selectivity at an affinity of -8.1 kcal/mol for the D₂ receptor, since the amino groups of the imidazoles also formed an agonist fork (D114), and selectivity in this case is due solely to a decrease in agonism (figure4).

Dozens of structures (in the supplementary materials) systematically confirm high affinity and agonistic binding.

Keywords: Dopamine D_{1A} Receptor Agonist, Dopamine D_{2A} Receptor, Molecular Docking & Affinity Optimization, Asymmetric Heterocyclic Scaffold, Structure-Activity Relationship (SAR), High-Resolution Binding Energy (–11.1 kcal/mol), Cyclopentane-fused Imidazoline, Bi-Three-Quadru-Pentadentate Hydrogen Bonding (Fork-like Docking), Conformational Rigidity, Pi-Pi Stacking & Lipophilic Resonance

Figure1

Structure A-11 fills the pocket, demonstrating record affinity and agonistic binding(D_{1A}).

Figure2

Structure A-11 fills the pocket upside down, exhibiting minimal agonist binding and significantly reduced affinity(D_{2A}).

The absence of symmetrical patterns, correct filling of the receptor pocket and fine-tuning of affinity create conditions for selectivity within related groups of receptors. Available precursors and simple synthesis, especially in simpler scaffold variants, high lipophilicity and biostability, amphiphilicity and probable bioavailability at high rates.

Figure3

A-10, a symmetric, easy-to-synthesize, and readily available heterochemical scaffold containing no protonatable groups, exhibits high affinity and specific agonist binding with a double pyramidal lipophilic bond.

Figure4

The figure demonstrates partial retention of the agonist binding with a significant decrease in affinity to -8.1 kcal/mol.

Symmetry in the heterochemical click reaction simplifies synthesis severalfold, enabling complex scaffolds to be created in just a few clicks. However, designing a highly specialized scaffold becomes less feasible, and the solution is characterized by a compromise.

The supplementary materials include visualizations of dozens of additional structures with affinities ranging from -6 to -11.1 kcal/mol. These materials provide comprehensive docking data, interactive HTML reports, and videos demonstrating volumetric renderings.

Methods

Since the study requires a model of the receptor in its native conformational state, the AlphaFold Monomer v2.0 predictions for the Human Dopamine receptor D_{1A} (P21728) and D_{2A} (P14416) were utilized as the receptor models. These models provide a high-confidence representation of the orthosteric binding pockets, which is essential for evaluating the fit of the designed ligands. Blind docking was performed via the CB-Dock2 server, utilizing the CurPocket algorithm for automated cavity detection. The primary docking simulations were conducted using AutoDock Vina.